

THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING EDUCATIONAL EFFICIENCY IN GENERAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS

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Abstract. *This article reflects on the role of the concept of innovation, which is currently actively used in all fields, in the field of education, in particular, its role in improving the effectiveness of education in general education schools.*

Keywords: *education, general education school, quality of education, effectiveness of education, innovation, innovative processes.*

In modern society, innovative technologies are expanding in almost all spheres of human activity, including education. Innovations in education - a new field of scientific and pedagogical knowledge; is considered as inseparable unity and interdependence of three main pedagogical processes in the field of education: creation of innovations, their assimilation and application. Based on the same, the following comments are made regarding innovative technologies in education and related processes.

The diversity and multidirectionality of innovative processes in the educational system is still an object of scientists and practitioners. Innovative processes in society are natural, objective in their own way, and constitute a necessary element of development. Their naturalness and objectivity is due to the accumulation of contradictions and problems for various reasons in any, even the most ideally organized social system, which reach different levels of intensity..

Innovation processes are open systems that are influenced by the environment, regardless of the field in which they are carried out. Without studying and taking into account the characteristics of the environment which is a part of the system and operates in it, it is impossible to understand the importance and essence of the system's functions, which, in turn, involves a broader analysis of the system.

Innovative technologies in education make it possible to organize education and direct it in the right direction. People have always been afraid of unknown and new things, they react negatively to any changes. Stereotypes existing in the public mind, affecting the usual way of life, lead to painful events, prevent the renewal of all types of education. The reason why people do not want to accept the innovations in modern education is because they block the vital needs for comfort, security, self-affirmation. Innovative behavior does not mean adaptation, it implies the formation of one's own personality, self-development.

The teacher should understand that innovative education is a way of educating a well-rounded person. "Ready-made templates" do not suit him, it is important to constantly improve his intellectual level. A teacher freed from "complexes" and psychological barriers is ready to become a full-fledged participant in innovative changes. One of the tasks of a modern school is to open the possibilities of all participants of the pedagogical process, to give them the opportunity to show their creative abilities. Solving these problems is not possible without implementing the variability

of educational processes, in connection with which there are various innovative types and kinds of educational institutions that require deep scientific and practical understanding.

Innovation is characteristic of any professional human activity and therefore naturally becomes an object of study, analysis and implementation. Innovations do not appear by themselves, they are the result of scientific research and advanced pedagogical experience of individual teachers and entire teams. This process cannot happen by itself, it must be managed, and this is the most important aspect of the practical process.

In conclusion, it can be said that innovative methods of teaching in secondary schools help to develop cognitive interest in students, they learn to systematize and summarize the studied material, discuss and debate. By perceiving and processing the acquired knowledge, students acquire the skills to apply them in practice, including communication experience. Undoubtedly, innovative teaching methods have advantages over traditional methods, because they contribute to the development of the student, teach him independence in knowledge and decision-making.

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